

A Hospital-Based Assessment of Locked Versus Non-Locked Plating of Distal Fibula Fractures: An Observational Study

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present was to compare the locked versus non-locked Plating of distal fibula fractures.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics, ESICMCH, Bihta, Bihar, India and reviewed a consecutive cohort of patients admitted within the 24-month period for fixation of closed malleolar fractures of the ankle. 200 patients with ankle fractures underwent surgical fixation with a distal fibular plate.

Results: Of the 200 patients, 120 (60%) received an STP, 30 (15%) an LC-DCP, and 50 (25%) an LCP-F. The mean interval to full weightbearing was 6.9 weeks for the STP group, 7.2 weeks for the LC-DCP group, and 7.6 weeks for the LCP-F group. Of the 200 patients, 8 had wound issues, 4 patients returned to the operating room for wound washout, and 12 required antibiotics.

Conclusion: In conclusion, bone-specific LCP-Fs add to the portfolio of implants available. They provide rigid fixation with a stable construct and thus are particularly attractive for multifragmentary fractures and patients with poor bone quality. Their unit cost is significantly greater than that of STPs and LC-DCPs but they provide a satisfactory alternative for those patients in whom and fracture patterns in which fixation is more likely to fail using non-locking techniques.

Keywords: ankle fracture, complications, locking plate trauma

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Introduction

Less compression of the periosteum is an advantage of a locking plate. [1-3] A non-locking conventional plate obtains the fixation stability by the frictional force between the plate and bone.¹ This compression could cause disturbances in blood supply to the bone and introduce an unfavourable condition for bone union. Therefore, the reduction of periosteal compression may improve the rate of bone union. Although many types of plates were developed, which do not interfere with the cortical blood flow, no clinical effectiveness of these plates has been clearly proven. [4-6]

The locking plate can be used in various ways; it may serve as a bridging plate, a compression plate, a tension band plate or a neutralization plate. [7-11] The use of a locking plate as a neutralization device for lag screw fracture fixation is one of the most important techniques for locking plate. [7] Most

displaced fractures of the lateral malleolus of ankle must be treated by anatomical reduction with absolute stability, and the fixation using a lag screw and neutralization plate is frequently performed.

In recent years, it has been pointed out that most of the comminuted fractures of distal fibula were caused by high-energy impact of pronation abduction. Moreover, high non-union rate of comminuted distal fibular fractures requires internal fixation for complete reduction. [12,13] To achieve a complete reduction in the comminuted fibula fractures, it is necessary to calibrate the length and rotation angle of the fibula. Clinically, common bone screws cannot fix the comminuted fractures of distal fibula, so it is imperative to discover a suitable treatment to cope with the difficult reduction.

Anatomical plate is a common material for fixation of fibular fractures. In terms of its mechanism of

action, the fracture site is compressed and fixed by the friction force generated when the bone surface is in close contact with anatomical plate so that the bone morphology is stably attached. [14] The double-hooked locking plate is a special deformation at the distal end of the locking plate. Owing to the double-hooked shape, the distal fibula fracture fragment can be pulled back for reduction. Moreover, the combination of the double-hooked locking plate and locking screws allows a firmer fixing of fibula fragments. Currently, double-hooked locking plates have been applied in external ankle fractures and achieved good clinical effect. [15,16]

The aim of the present was to compare the locked versus non-locked Plating of distal fibula fractures.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics, ESICMCH, Bihta, Bihar, India and reviewed a consecutive cohort of patients admitted within the 24-month period for fixation of closed malleolar fractures of the ankle. 200 patients with ankle fractures underwent surgical fixation with a distal fibular plate. Open ankle fractures, pilon fractures, injuries treated with an external fixator, fractures treated with syndesmotic screws only, and isolated medial malleolar fractures were excluded. Complications, including reoperation and subsequent removal of hardware, were recorded from the clinical data for the next 2 years.

Operative Technique

All patients received antibiotic prophylaxis with a single dose of a second-generation cephalosporin unless allergic to penicillin, in which case they received teicoplanin according to the hospital protocol. The choice of implant and use of lag screws was left to the discretion of the operating surgeon. The implants available during the study period were a one-third semi tubular plate (STP), a 3.5-mm limited-contact dynamic compression plate (LC-DCP), and a 2.7-mm/3.5-mm locking compression distal fibula plate (LCP-F). All 3 plates were manufactured by DePuy Synthes (West Chester, PA). Drains were not routinely used. All patients received low-molecular-weight heparin as thromboprophylaxis from 6 hours postoperatively for the duration of plaster cast immobilization. Radiographs were obtained at 6 weeks postoperatively and at further follow-up examinations, if deemed necessary, until clinical and radiographic union were achieved.

Analysis of Findings

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, version 22 (IBM, Armonk, NY). Data were tested for normality using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The results were considered statistically significant at $p \leq .05$.

Results

Table 1: Patent and clinical characteristics

Characteristics	Semi tubular Plate (n = 120)	Limited-Contact Dynamic Compression Plate (n = 30)	Locking Compression Distal Fibula Plate (n = 50)
Age (y) Mean \pm SD	40 \pm 15.5	39 \pm 16.4	58 \pm 15.5
Gender	64	18	21
Male			
Female	56	12	29
Diabetes mellitus	2	0	7
Fracture type			
Lateral malleolus	48	8	7
Bimalleolar	54	16	24
Trimalleolar	18	6	19
Weber A	1	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Weber B	100	12	48
Weber C	19	18	2
Lag screw fixation	108	15	24

Of the 200 patients, 120 (60%) received an STP, 30 (15%) an LC-DCP, and 50 (25%) an LCP-F.

Table 2: Outcome measures

Outcomes	Semi tubular Plate (n = 120)	Limited-Contact Dynamic Compression Plate (n = 30)	Locking Compression Distal Fibula Plate (n = 50)
Radiographic union (wk)			
Mean	15.3	15.5	14.4
Median	12.0	12.0	12.0
95% CI	12.0 to 16.5	11.9 to 21.4	11.4 to 17.1
Full weight bearing (wk)			
Mean	6.9	7.2	7.6
Median	6.0	6.0	7.5
95% CI	6.5 to 7.4	6.3 to 8.1	6.6 to 8.5

The mean interval to full weightbearing was 6.9 weeks for the STP group, 7.2 weeks for the LC-DCP group, and 7.6 weeks for the LCP-F group.

Table 3: Complications and reoperations

Variables	Semi tubular Plate (n = 120)	Limited-Contact Dynamic Compression Plate (n = 30)	Locking Compression Distal Fibula Plate (n = 50)
Complications			
None identified	112	27	44
Infection requiring washout	3	1	2
Superficial infection requiring antibiotics	5	3	4
Wound issues not requiring antibiotics	7	0	1
Reoperation			
Washout with or without removal of metalwork	2	1	1
Planned removal of syndesmosis screw	6	2	0
Removal of symptomatic metalwork	15	3	1
Revision	5	0	2

Of the 200 patients, 8 had wound issues, 4 patients returned to the operating room for wound washout, and 12 required antibiotics.

Discussion

Ankle malleolar fractures are common injuries, constituting approximately 9% of all fractures. [17] With the incidence and severity of ankle fractures in the elderly population increasing, osteoporosis could increase the level of difficulty involved with surgical management of ankle fractures. [18-20]

The technique of surgical fixation used can be influenced by the fracture pattern, soft tissue injury, and bone quality. Conventional fracture plating systems depend on adequate bone quality to achieve sound fixation and maintain construct stability. Loosening or toggling of screws as a result of poor fixation, with resulting loss of friction between the plate and bone, can lead to failure of fixation.²⁰ Fixed-angle locking plates are useful with poor bone quality because they do not rely on screw-plate friction: rather, the threaded screw head locks into a

threaded plate aperture. Precontoured plates also facilitate fixation, placement, and accuracy. [21] However, locking plates can have greater rigidity compared with conventional plates, which can impair fracture healing. [22] Of the 200 patients, 120 (60%) received an STP, 30 (15%) an LC-DCP, and 50 (25%) an LCP-F. The mean interval to full weightbearing was 6.9 weeks for the STP group, 7.2 weeks for the LC-DCP group, and 7.6 weeks for the LCP-F group. Of the 200 patients, 8 had wound issues, 4 patients returned to the operating room for wound washout, and 12 required antibiotics.

Biomechanical studies conducted on cadavers have shown that contoured locking plates for distal fibular fractures in osteoporotic bone have greater torque and angle at failure compared with conventional plates. [23] It was also found that a locking plate construct with 2 distal unicortical screws was mechanically equivalent to a standard plate with 3 distal screws in cadavers. [24] These biomechanical studies have shown that although fixation with standard plates is dependent on bone

mineral density, the locking plate is not, with the implication that these plates will be advantageous in osteoporotic bone. However, in patients with normal bone mineral density and no fracture comminution, locking plates do not offer a mechanical advantage compared with the nonlocking alternatives. [25]

Schepers et al [26], in a retrospective study of 165 patients, found increased wound complications in distal fibular fractures treated with locking compression plate compared with semi tubular plates and cautioned against their use. Although no difference was found between their groups in terms of removal of hardware, their overall wound complication rate was 17.5% with locking plates compared with 5.5% with semi tubular plates. Tsukada et al [27] conducted a randomized controlled trial of 52 patients and found no difference in complication rates or the time to radiographic bone union between locking and nonlocking plates; a finding also supported by our study. The LCP-F implant is more expensive (~£500) than a standard fibula fixation construct. However, this should be balanced against the cost of further intervention for patients in whom osteoporotic bone or unstable fractures could be expected to increase the risk of displacement requiring further surgery. [28]

Conclusion

In conclusion, bone-specific LCP-Fs add to the portfolio of implants available. They provide rigid fixation with a stable construct and thus are particularly attractive for multifragmentary fractures and patients with poor bone quality. Their unit cost is significantly greater than that of STPs and LC-DCPs but they provide a satisfactory alternative for those patients in whom and fracture patterns in which fixation is more likely to fail using nonlocking techniques.

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